

ADVANTAGES OF USING INTERACTIVE PLATFORMS TO TEACH ENGLISH VOCABULARY

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Abstract. *Vocabulary has a significant impact on language proficiency. In today's world, employing new ways to teach vocabulary is becoming increasingly important, therefore using interactive platforms is an excellent example of selecting an effective way to teach vocabulary. The paper's research approach is the synthesis method (qualitative), which is the act of synthesizing the findings of many primary research investigations aimed at testing a single conceptual premise.*

Keywords: *teaching English, interactive platforms, English vocabulary.*

Vocabulary is a component of linguistic abilities including reading, speaking, listening, and writing. According to Nation (2013), vocabulary items are critical in the acquisition of the four language skills: hearing, speaking, reading, and writing.

The utilization of innovative technology for language teaching has become the ideal complement to a comprehensive education, helping students to achieve flawless English proficiency. Language classes that include an online learning solution are more efficient, flexible, and entertaining for learners, particularly digital natives who are accustomed to utilizing smartphones for most daily tasks.

The usage of learning methods is critical and deserves special consideration in the student's life. We live in a digital age, and everyone expects something efficient, effective, dynamic, rapid, and engaging. The term 'interactive' emerges in two independent strands of educational research discourse: one on pedagogy and another about innovative educational technologies.

Teaching students using traditional approaches with only one mode of communication is no longer effective. The term 'interactive' refers to an effective and efficient teaching and learning process in which the teacher can capture learners' attention and learners can learn more than in the traditional technique.

Teachers can now use a variety of digital tools to supplement traditional classroom instruction. Educational technology has made lessons more fascinating, engaging, and interactive. E-learning systems also allow for the implementation of tried-and-true blended learning or flipped classes. Both systems take a hybrid approach, encouraging learners' flexibility and autonomy. They also give teachers a variety of exercises and activities for different levels to enhance student engagement in the classroom.

On the one hand, they give educational institutions the most effective and efficient control over tasks such as activating student accounts, creating groups, sending automatic emails and notifications, and so on. On the other hand, crucial duties such as tracking student progress through software can now be used to determine whether or not goals for activities or exercises to be reviewed in class have been met.

Innovative technology enables pupils to be more creative and engaged in the classroom. They build a foundation of knowledge outside of the classroom by engaging with all of the course material, and when they return to the classroom, they share that knowledge. Educational technology helps students prepare for class and gives professors with engaging resources to make

their classes more human and sociable. All pupils have the opportunity to engage in all activities. As a result, employing interactive platforms to teach English provides various benefits, including engagement, personalization, quick feedback, accessibility, collaboration, progress tracking, and incentives.

Interactive platforms make learning more interesting and enjoyable for pupils. Gamified games, quizzes, and interactive exercises help students stay motivated and focused on studying. Calvo-Ferrer (2017) investigated the influence of computer games on language learning. His experimental group learned new vocabulary using computer games, whereas the control group practiced language through other activities (such as vocabulary exercises in their textbooks).

After analyzing the results of the pre-test and post-test that he administered to both groups, he discovered that pupils who were allowed to utilize computer games performed substantially better in the short run than those who employed alternative methods of practicing vocabulary. Furthermore, students in the experimental group said that computer games were enjoyable and helped them improve their vocabulary. Segers and Verhoeven (2003) investigated the impact of intense vocabulary teaching using computer games in kindergartens in the Netherlands. A hundred and sixty-four students took part in the 15-week study.

During this time, 67 students from the experimental group played computer games for 15 minutes twice a week, while 97 children from the control group completed the standard curriculum. Their findings revealed that computer games improved children's vocabularies.

These platforms frequently provide personalized learning experiences by adapting to the particular needs and success of each student. This allows students to learn at their own pace and focus on areas that require more experience.

Students can fix mistakes and reinforce learning in real-time via interactive platforms, which provide quick feedback. Immediate feedback can help kids better learn subjects and retain terminology.

Students can now access interactive platforms from anywhere, making learning more flexible and easier. This accessibility enables students to practice English vocabulary outside of the classroom, which can improve retention and proficiency. Many interactive platforms incorporate features that encourage student cooperation, improve communication skills, and create teamwork. Interactive platforms frequently incorporate tools that enable teachers and students to track progress, assess performance, and discover areas for development. This data-driven strategy can assist educators in tailoring their teaching tactics and providing tailored support to pupils.

To motivate students to meet their learning objectives, interactive platforms can include incentives, badges, leaderboards, and other motivators. These motivating factors might boost student engagement and persistence in learning English vocabulary.

Conclusion

When applied together with traditional teaching, new technology can diversify educational centers, pushing English instruction to the next level by focusing on diversity in the classroom and improving the language learning experience. Investing in technological tools to improve language learning is not only a way to improve educational quality, but also a way to maximize the material benefits of internationalization, such as increased funding and revenue generation, strengthened international capacity building, and improved research and development. Overall, employing interactive platforms to teach English vocabulary can make students' learning experiences more pleasurable, effective, and engaging, resulting in better language acquisition outcomes.

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